

THERMAL RESIDUAL STRAIN MEASUREMENT IN A COMPOSITE REPAIR ON A CRACKED ALUMINUM STRUCTURE

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SUMMARY: This paper reports results related to thermally induced and process generated residual strains present in a repaired structure consisting of boron/epoxy patches bonded to a cracked aluminum specimen using FM 73M. To measure residual strains within the aluminum and boron/epoxy materials, 44 strain gauges were installed in eight locations at different interfaces of one bonded repair during patch construction and application. The stress free temperature was determined for the repair and found to be well below the curing temperature of 121°C. At room temperature, thermal residual strain magnitudes up to 690 $\mu\epsilon$ in the aluminum and -710 $\mu\epsilon$ in the boron/epoxy patch were measured. In addition, process induced strains were found to be present in the aluminum and oriented perpendicular to the boron fibers. The thermal residual strains present in the bonded repair were also investigated as a function of temperature and indicated a significant change in slope above 90°C.

KEYWORDS: thermal residual strain, residual strain, bonded repair, crack patching, aircraft, film adhesive, boron, aluminum

INTRODUCTION

In the application of composite patches to aluminum aircraft structures, consideration must be given to the residual strain distribution introduced during the repair process. In most composite repairs, the underlying structure is heated locally during the curing process. The unheated surrounding structure will restrain the expansion of the heated area, which leads to a lower effective coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) for the repaired substructure. In addition, the supporting structure of an aircraft frame will limit the out-of-plane bending and resulting curvature of a single sided repair, which is also caused by the difference in CTE. The magnitude of the thermally induced residual strains (referred to subsequently as thermal residual strains) is therefore dependent upon the difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion between the composite and aluminum as well as the heating and support conditions [2,4].

In contrast to real structure conditions, most materials and procedures are tested using specimens which are typically uniformly heated during the curing process and permitted to expand with little or no restraint (Fig. 1). The key is to understand the relationship between the constraint conditions of the test specimen relative to those of the damaged aircraft structure such that the thermal residual strains can be accounted for properly in the determination of the margin of safety.

Fig. 1: Small Scale Test Specimen for Composite Repairs [3]

A significant effort has been made through a joint research project between the University of British Columbia (UBC) and the National Research Council of Canada (NRC) to improve the knowledge and potential effect of residual strains induced by the elevated temperature cure in bonded repairs. The magnitude of these residual strains will not only affect the crack propagation life component of a bonded repair, but will also influence the time required for re-initiation of a fatigue crack in the metallic substructure, especially in the presence of a corrosive environment. Although thermal residual strains are the primary focus of this work, the total residual strain due to the elevated temperature cure of any bonded repair consists of both thermal and process induced residual strains, the latter resulting from effects such as anisotropic shrinkage of the patch or adhesive, temperature gradients in the specimen during processing, temperature gradients due to tooling and internal resin flow [6]. While thermal strains are affected by subsequent changes in temperature, process induced residual strains may not be affected. This paper will discuss the results obtained from experimental measurements of residual strain for the bonded repair specimen shown in Fig. 1.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

AMRL Test Specimen

The sandwich type specimen (Fig. 1) used in this investigation, which limits out-of-plane bending due to the honeycomb structure, was developed previously by the Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory (AMRL) in Australia. A specially designed fixture employed for the assembly and curing process allowed free in-plane expansion to occur during the cure. Boron/epoxy 5521/4 prepreg, FM 73M film adhesive with a nominal weight of 300 g/m^2 , precracked 2024-T3 aluminum alloy sheets with a thickness of 3.175 mm and HEXCEL honeycomb 3/16-5052-.002 were selected as materials for the specimen. A total of 44 metal

foil strain gauges were employed to monitor the thermal residual strains and total residual strains due to the elevated temperature cure at several locations of the composite repair on one of the two patched face-sheets of the specimen (Fig. 2). Four locations were chosen based on previous documentation which indicated failure initiation sites of the bonded repair occurring around the crack in the aluminum as well as at the tapered end of the patch [1,5]. Within the patched region, strain gauges were placed on each side of the aluminum face-sheet, on top of the adhesive, between the first and second boron/epoxy plies and on top of the patch. In addition, two rosettes were placed outside the repair section on the aluminum face-sheet. Careful planning of the gauge positions and lead wire routing (Fig. 2) was performed to minimize distortions of the true strain distribution.

Fig. 2: Instrumented AMRL Specimen

Specimen preparation was divided into five steps: 1) preparation of the face-sheets, 2) gauge mounting on the face-sheets, 3) patch manufacturing including gauge placement, 4) specimen assembly and 5) final gauge installation. First, the aluminum face-sheets were precracked to a crack length of 20 mm. Surface treatment of the aluminum for the bonding process consisted of clad removal, grit blasting with size 220 aluminum oxide grit, a silane treatment and subsequent application of BR 127 primer. Six two-element (90°) and two three-element strain gauge rosettes were then installed in the patch section on both sides of the aluminum face-sheet.

The seven boron/epoxy prepreg plies for each patch were cut in a semi-circular shape with the fiber orientation parallel to the straight edge. The plies were tapered using a 3 mm step between successive plies. The longer outer plies were placed over the inner shorter during lay-up. To minimize distortion of the true strain field, only single element gauges with two 34 gauge lead wires were embedded within the patch. The cocured layer of FM 73M was extended to a rectangular-shape extending beyond the semi-circular shaped seven plies of boron/epoxy prepreg to permit terminal placement and connection of the lead wires, thus avoiding the need to handle the fine diameter lead wires after curing. The patch was C-scanned and X-rayed to check for disbonds and to verify the strain gauge locations after curing at 121°C and 345 kPa pressure.

The bottom of the patches were then grit blasted prior to specimen assembly, which removed a thin layer of the cocured FM 73M. The specimen was then assembled in the aluminum fixture. Single layers of FM 73M were used for bonding the patches to the aluminum. The assembled specimen in the fixture was then cured in the autoclave at 121°C with 345 kPa pressure. In total, 28 gauges were installed at this stage. After removal and clean-up, spacers and shims were installed in the grip region using the room curing adhesive HYSOL EA 9396.

The last step in the instrumented specimen preparation process was the installation of eight, two-element (90°) strain gauges on top of the instrumented patch and outside the repair section. A maximum of two gauges were installed at any one time using M-Bond 610, resulting in the need for four curing cycles. To limit the influence of thermal cycling, the strain gauge glue was cured at 100°C. A final post-cure was then carried out at 107.2°C, which was the highest temperature anticipated for the thermal experiments. This completed the installation of the 44 strain gauges.

Stress Free Temperature

Determination of the thermal residual strains at room temperature requires knowledge of the stress free temperature at which no thermal residual strains are present. In order to determine the stress free temperature for the current application, one identical patch was bonded to a 152.4 mm x 152.4 mm aluminum alloy sheet using one layer of FM 73M. The residual strains caused a significant curvature in the aluminum sheet. To determine the stress free temperature (assuming that process induced strains are negligible in the fiber direction), the specimen was heated until the specimen returned to its initial straight condition in the fiber direction.

This measurement was carried out using a Blue M industrial oven equipped with a Microtrol controller. The specimen was supported with a flat steel bar and a pin (Fig. 3). A halogen light was used to clearly indicate the presence of any gap existing between the curved aluminum sheet and the flat steel bar.

Fig. 3: Stress Free Temperature Measurement Setup

Both the oven and aluminum sheet temperatures were monitored using thermocouples. At 101.25°C, with both the specimen and oven being in thermal equilibrium, the single-side patched aluminum sheet was straight along the supported edge. This experimental set-up had an estimated potential error of 1.5°C based on the stated assumptions (i.e. potential resolution error of 0.5°C + potential temperature measurement error of < 1°C using listed device specifications).

Residual Strain Measurement Procedure

To determine the magnitude of the total residual strains introduced during curing requires knowledge of the strain state both prior to and after completion of the thermal cycle. The strain state prior to curing was obtained using two Vishay 2310 signal conditioning amplifiers, one each for the 120 Ω and 350 Ω quarter bridge configurations. At this point, 120 Ω and 350 Ω precision resistors, respectively, were used in the quarter bridge to zero the two signal conditioning amplifiers. The precision resistors were then removed and replaced by the mounted strain gauges, one gauge at a time, with the indicated resistance change (i.e. strain) being recorded. Since cocuring of the one layer of FM 73M with the seven boron/epoxy plies had introduced some residual stresses in the patch itself (as indicated by the slightly curved patch), the patch was vacuum bagged against a flat aluminum plate for the initial strain recordings to provide a repeatable and representative measurement condition both pre- and post-cure. While this flat patch geometry was representative of the pre-curing setup in the autoclave, it should be noted that the peel ply on the bottom of the patch was not removed for this measurement to protect the bonding surface from contamination. After curing, this measurement condition (including temperature conditions) was maintained and the strain measurement recording procedure repeated. The total residual strains induced during the curing cycle were then determined by calculating the difference in the pre- and post cure strain measurements.

Thermal Residual Strain Measurement Procedure

To quantify the thermal residual strains within the repaired specimen, it was decided to heat the specimen up to the stress free temperature. However, accurate determination of the thermal residual strains in the bonded repair required the measurement of not only thermal strains in the AMRL specimen, but also measurement of the thermal strains for an additional aluminum and a cured boron/epoxy specimen as shown by equations (1) and (2) below.

$$\epsilon_{Al \text{ Thermal Residual}}|_T = \epsilon_{Al}|_{T=Stress \text{ Free Temp.}} - \epsilon_{AMRL}|_{T=Stress \text{ Free Temp.}} - \epsilon_{Al}|_T + \epsilon_{AMRL}|_T \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_{B/Ep \text{ Thermal Residual}}|_T = \epsilon_{B/Ep}|_{T=Stress \text{ Free Temp.}} - \epsilon_{AMRL}|_{T=Stress \text{ Free Temp.}} - \epsilon_{B/Ep}|_T + \epsilon_{AMRL}|_T \quad (2)$$

In addition, to determine the actual strain experienced by each of the different installed strain gauges, one identical gauge of each type was mounted on a titanium silicate bar having a coefficient of thermal expansion of only $0.03 \pm 0.03 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$. The difference in indicated strain between an identical gauge mounted on a specimen and on the titanium silicate bar thus represents the actual thermal strain in the specimen according to equation (3) below:

$$\epsilon_{Specimen \text{ Thermal}}|_T = \epsilon_{Specimen \text{ (Indicated)}}|_T - \epsilon_{Titanium \text{ Silicate (Indicated)}}|_T \quad (3)$$

The temperature of the AMRL specimen and the titanium silicate bar were both measured using bonded thermocouples. Three-wire strain gauge bridge configurations providing thermal compensation were installed between the terminal blocks mounted on the specimens and the data acquisition system. Measurements of resistance change per $^\circ\text{C}$ and per mm of lead wire length between the strain gauge and terminal blocks were obtained from a lead wire resistance specimen and were subsequently used for strain data correction. To minimize thermal shock, the instrumented AMRL specimen together with the titanium silicate bar and the lead wire resistance measurement specimen were wrapped in breather cloth and covered

with a thin aluminum foil. The same protection was provided for the instrumented aluminum and the boron/epoxy specimens. A Schlumberger Orion datalogger utilizing a high stability, dual current technique allowed simultaneous acquisition of temperature, wire resistance and strain gauge data. To avoid any potential heating effects due to power dissipation at the strain gauge sites, only gauges within a single interface (i.e. ply, layer, etc.) were measured during any single test.

The difference in thermal conductivity and mass between the AMRL and titanium silicate specimens caused a significant difference in the rate of temperature change. Therefore it was decided to establish thermal equilibrium between the specimens and the oven temperature at 21°C (room temperature), 50°C, 80°C and 107°C. The measurements were carried out both during the heating and cooling portions of the thermal cycles. Approximately two hours were required to achieve thermal equilibrium at each of these specified temperatures. To confirm repeatability of the results, measurements were repeated for 12 gauges. For comparison, measurements were also obtained using a 3 fold increase in heating and cooling rates.

All of the recorded strain measurements were subsequently corrected for gauge factor changes due to temperature, lead wire resistance as well as temperature-induced lead wire resistance change, and transverse strain sensitivity for rosettes. The transverse strain sensitivity was estimated to have very little effect on the thermal residual strains for the single element gauges mounted in the boron/epoxy patch (on the order of 0.1%).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The corrected results obtained for the thermal residual strains and the total residual strains due to the elevated temperature cure are presented in Fig. 4. The thermal residual strains were calculated based on the temperature difference between the measured stress free temperature (101.25°C) and 21°C. It should be noted that the thermal residual strains are averaged results based on data obtained from the heating and cooling cycles as well as repeated measurements. Holding for extended periods of time at elevated temperatures caused detectable strain due to creep in the bonded repair, especially perpendicular to the fiber direction (on average < 20 $\mu\epsilon$ with maximum of 90 $\mu\epsilon$ at the tapered end in 55 minutes at 80°C). Very little strain hysteresis due to creep was measured when the experiment was carried out at higher heating and cooling rates without holding at the elevated temperatures. Based on this evidence, the thermal residual strain measurements recorded were corrected for creep while holding at elevated temperatures.

The thermal residual strains for the aluminum within the center section of the repair (specimen locations 'B', 'C', 'D' and 'H') vary in fiber direction of the patch between 491 $\mu\epsilon$ and 686 $\mu\epsilon$ with an average of 541 $\mu\epsilon$ (standard deviation of 14%). The total residual strains due to the elevated temperature cure are very close to this result with an average of 546 $\mu\epsilon$ (standard deviation of 16%), which indicates that process induced strains present are essentially negligible in this direction. In contrast, the total residual strain average due to the elevated temperature cure measured in the aluminum perpendicular to the fiber direction of the patch at these same locations (-164 $\mu\epsilon$ with a standard deviation of 44%) is significantly higher in compression than the thermal residual strain average of -111 $\mu\epsilon$ (with a standard deviation of 20%) indicating that process induced strains are substantially higher in this direction. Unfortunately, the possibility of residual strain relaxation during the first few thermal cycles cannot be verified.

Fig. 4: Thermal Residual and Total Residual Strains due to Elevated Temperature Cure

The thermal residual strains for the boron/epoxy patch at these four locations decline from an average of $-638 \mu\epsilon$ at the patch adhesive interface to $-572 \mu\epsilon$ on top of the patch (standard deviations $< 6\%$). It is important to note that the initial strain state of the boron/epoxy patch cocured with one layer of FM 73M was not identical to the seven ply boron/epoxy specimen which was used for the thermal residual strain measurement thus not allowing identification of process induced strains. In addition, the peel ply was removed after the initial measurement and the bottom of the patch grit blasted, both of which will have an effect on the initial strain

state. The cause for the very large discrepancy in the measured thermal residual strains and total residual strains due to the elevated temperature cure in the boron/epoxy at specimen location 'A' has not yet been identified.

The maximum thermal residual strains found at the strain gauged locations were close to $690 \mu\epsilon$ at the aluminum/adhesive interface (see specimen location 'B'), which is approximately 15% of the aluminum yield strain and should therefore be carefully considered for the determination of the margin of safety of a bonded repair. The thermal residual strains in the boron/epoxy exceeded $-710 \mu\epsilon$ (see specimen location 'G') which can be a concern for repairs under compression loading.

Fig. 5 shows the thermal residual strains versus the temperature for the higher heating rate at specimen location 'B' close to the crack tip. The curves show the thermal residual strains of the aluminum in both the longitudinal and transverse directions of the specimen and at the interface between the adhesive and the first boron/epoxy ply in fiber direction. The thermal residual strains for the aluminum are decreasing nearly linearly with temperature up to approximately 85°C . Above 90°C the change in the thermal residual strain with temperature is small, i.e. the boron/epoxy patch and the aluminum expand nearly at their unrestrained rates.

Fig. 5: Thermal Residual Strain versus Temperature

The thermal residual strain versus temperature for the boron/epoxy is initially linear up to approximately 65°C . At this temperature the slope changes slightly and continues to be approximately linear to around 85°C . Above 90°C the residual thermal strain in the boron/epoxy changes only slightly with trends corresponding to those of the aluminum. Note that the thermal strain in the boron/epoxy specimen shows a linear relationship with temperature for the employed temperature range. A possible cause might be the penetration of FM 73 into the boron/epoxy, resulting in the presence of two epoxies with different thermal properties in the patch.

Error estimates indicate that the maximum variation due to hysteresis during these tests was $31 \mu\epsilon$ with an average of only $9 \mu\epsilon$, which does not include creep while holding at elevated temperatures during the experiments. It was noted that an error of 1% in the gauge factor

leads to a change of up to $8 \mu\epsilon$ in the thermal residual strain while the maximum uncertainty of 10 mm in the length of the lead wires connecting the strain gauges with the terminals will only result in an error of $4 \mu\epsilon$. Errors regarding the absolute resistance of all lead wires can be neglected. An error of 2°C in the stress free temperature was found to have only a small effect (approximately $1 \mu\epsilon$).

In summary, the results provided here for a bonded repair utilizing FM 73M indicate that using the difference between the curing and ambient temperature as input to a thermal residual strain model may substantially over-estimate the thermal residual strains present in the repaired structure. Approximately $855 \mu\epsilon$ are predicted using a conventional closed form solution for the uncracked metallic component of a reinforced specimen [1] which is nearly 60% higher than the measured average of $541 \mu\epsilon$ for the cracked aluminum within the center section of the AMRL specimen repair. Unfortunately, the more general question of the real benefit of a lower temperature cure (80°C) for FM 73M cannot be answered at this point since more detailed experiments are required to show the thermal residual strain versus temperature behavior. In addition, the effect of temperature on crack growth retardation in the aluminum must also be considered in any comparison to assess the actual benefits of lower curing temperatures.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Thermal residual strains as well as the total residual strains due to the elevated temperature cure were measured using an instrumented sandwich type AMRL specimen. The results indicate that although the FM 73M film adhesive was cured at 121°C and the specimen exhibited a stress free temperature of 101.25°C as determined from current testing, thermal residual strains remained linear with temperature only up to 90°C , beyond which the thermal residual strain gradient was substantially reduced. This phenomenon reduces the expected thermal residual strains at room temperature significantly and suggest that current models employing temperature differences between cure and ambient may substantially over-estimate the magnitude of this residual strain component.

Thermal residual strains at defined strain gauged locations were found to be as high as $690 \mu\epsilon$ in the aluminum (approximately 15% of yield) and $-710 \mu\epsilon$ in the boron/epoxy patch. The results obtained for the thermal residual strains and total residual strains due to the elevated temperature cure for the aluminum in the longitudinal direction of the specimen were found to be nearly equivalent, while it is believed that the difference in the transverse direction of the specimen is caused by process induced strains such as adhesive shrinkage. Although of definite interest, the thermal residual strains and the total residual strains due to the elevated temperature cure for the boron/epoxy cannot be directly compared due to the different initial conditions.

Although the magnitude of thermal residual strains will be less in a constrained structure [7], they should be carefully considered to determine the margin of safety of a bonded repair. The incorporation of thermal residual strains is important for the performance comparison of bonded repairs especially if test specimens with different constraint conditions are used. Continuing work, including a finite element analysis, is being carried out to model the thermal residual strain distribution and dependence on temperature. The results of this work will be correlated with the current results and subsequently utilized to compare with the predict

capabilities of currently available theoretical models. In addition, further experiments are planned to verify the thermal residual strain characteristics of FM 73M film adhesive and to assess thermal residual strains in the high temperature cured AMRL specimen at low temperatures. Further work to quantify the thermal residual strains for the 80°C cure are also being planned in order to establish the actual benefit of lowering the curing temperature.

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